

CREATION OF PRODUCTIVE VARIETIES OF COTTON FROM THE NEWLY CREATED RIDGES OF TYPE-IV OF FIBER

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Abstract. This article praeidis information about fertile created cotton which praedes type IV like feбри and creating new typer of cotton.

Keywords: Fiber, system, model, microneur, type fiber, fiber hardness, fiber quality.

In the countries of the world, extensive research is being carried out on the development of cotton cultivation, in particular, without expanding the cotton cultivation areas, in addition to increasing the quantity and improving the quality of the harvest, special attention is paid to the creation of varieties naturally resistant to cotton pests. Important results have been achieved in cotton selection on the basis of researches on the creation of new varieties with high yield, high yield and high seed fertility.

The purpose of the research is to create varieties suitable for different soil-climatic conditions of Fergana region, quick-ripening, productive, with high seed moisture content and high fiber yield and technological quality indicators, 4, 6, 8, 11, 14, 15 and 17, 30, 76 rows were also planted in the experimental field at PSUEAITI Andijan ITS, and observation and calculation work was carried out on the relevant indicators specified in the program.

In our country today, planting varieties with high economic value in cotton fields allows to increase productivity and improve the quality of cotton fiber without spending additional labor and money. This is the important contribution of breeding scientists to further development of cotton farming.

Cotton yield formation is a more complex trait. Yield is determined by the number of bolls on a cotton plant and the weight of cotton per boll. At the same time, productivity depends on many other characteristics - for example, early maturity, resistance to diseases and pests, and the adaptability of the variety to the influence of changing environmental conditions.

Precociousness is usually related to yield in a curve. Therefore, not the correlation coefficient of these signs, but the correlation relationship is calculated. From the curve between earliness and yield, the earliest forms are

the least productive. As the growing season lengthens, the yield increases up to a certain limit, and in very late forms, the yield begins to decrease again.

In the researches conducted by us, the yield criterion of the ridges is considered the main indicators of the experience. As can be seen from the obtained data, in 2015, the 14th ridge gave the highest yield among the ridges (42.1 t/ha), and an additional yield of 5.2 t/ha was obtained compared to the model variety. A similar result is 17; 30; It was also observed in 76 ridges. In the first year of the study, this line also gave an additional yield of 5.1 t/ha compared to the control variety (42 t/ha), showing relatively high productivity among the lines.

From the ridges, the 11th ridge yielded 34.9 t/ha, showing a low yield both compared to the model and compared to other ridges. The rest of the ridges yielded slightly higher yields than the control.

In the experiment, it can be seen from the data obtained in 2016 that among the ridges, ridges 8,14 and 17,30,76 gave the highest yield (respectively 42.2; 41.7 and 41.3; 41.8; 41.7 ts/ha sample It was shown that it has an additional yield of 5.0, 4.5 and 4.1 ts/ha compared to the variety. From the ridges, the 15th ridge yielded 36.3 t/ha, showing a lower yield compared to the model and compared to other ridges. The rest of the ridges yielded a yield close to and slightly higher than the control, and the model did not differ significantly from the variety and from each other in terms of this indicator.

When analyzing the yield data obtained in the experiment in 2017, the highest yields among the ridges were ridge 14 (41.9 ts/ha) and ridge 17 (40.8 ts/ha), with 5.3 and 4.2 compared to the model variety. gave an additional yield to ts/ha. Among the low-yielding ridges, the results observed in other years of the experiment were almost repeated, that is, the 11th and 15th ridges yielded 36.8 and 37.3 t/ha, showing a significant low yield among the ridges and in comparison to the sample variety.

The results of the three-year analysis of the studied productivity data show that the highest productivity among the ridges was observed in the 14th ridge. This ridge showed a yield of 41.9 tons/ha, giving an additional yield of 5.0 tons/ha compared to the model. Similar results were observed in rows 30 and 76, yielding 41.8 and 41.7 t/ha, respectively. These results are 4.9 and 4.8 ts/h higher than the sample variety Andijon-35. When talking about other lines, it should be mentioned that they also gave a slightly higher yield compared to the control variety, only the 11th line achieved an average yield of 36.3 t/ha in three years, showing that it was 0.6 t/ha less than the control.

Table 1

Productivity of ridges according to the years of the experiment, ts/ha.

Template and ridges	Years			Average	The difference template variety %
	2015	2016	2017		
Andijan - 35	36,9	37,2	36,6	36,9	-
1 - ridge	37,7	38,1	39,0	38,2	+1,3
3- ridge	37,4	38,3	39,6	38,4	+1,5
4- ridge	38,3	40,4	39,3	39,3	+2,4
6- ridge	37,4	39,1	37,8	38,0	+1,1
8- ridge	37,5	42,2	39,5	40,0	+3,1
11- ridge	34,9	37,5	36,8	36,3	-0,6
14- ridge	42,1	41,7	41,9	41,9	+5,0
15- ridge	37,6	36,3	37,3	37,0	+0,1
17- ridge	42,0	41,3	40,8	41,3	+4,4
30- ridge	42,0	41,6	41,8	41,8	+4,7
76- ridge	42,0	41,5	41,5	41,7	+4,8

It should be noted that the ridges that have been showing the most positive indicators since their early stages are ridges 14 and 17-30. In the future, as a result of observation and calculations, if these ridges can achieve positive results in terms of economic value, technological indicators of fiber, moisture content, and aspects of economic efficiency obtained from them, it will be the basis for submitting them to the variety testing center of the State Variety Testing for the creation of new varieties.

The main technological indicators of fiber quality are the hardness and thinness of a single fiber - the metric number that determines its length. Depending on these main indicators, different types of fiber are included in different industrial types. The hardness and fineness of the fiber varies strongly depending on the conditions of cotton care. The maturity, heredity of technological quality, and length of cotton fibers grown in agronomically neglected lands, which are not provided with enough water, do not

correspond to the norms specific to their type. Initially, the heritability of technological quality of fiber was not studied at a high level due to the difficulty of analysis and the lack of opportunity to examine large populations for this trait.

Based on the above considerations, it is necessary that the cotton varieties being created meet the requirements in terms of all parameters of the fiber, for example, the metric number of the fiber must be on average 5750-5900, and the length of the fiber must be at least 33 mm. In general, the fiber of the newly created varieties should be of high quality.

For this, the goal is achieved only if the initial material used in the selection (parental forms) is long and soft. Special importance should be given to the maternal form participating in breeding.

When analyzing the technological characteristics of the fiber of the 2015 cotton crop, it was found that the fibers of type IV, i.e., 1st, 6th, 14th and 17th, 30th, 76th ridges have high fiber quality according to the metric number (respectively 5700; 5810; 5900 and 5740; 5890; 5740) were identified.

It is worth mentioning that in the years of research in the competition nursery, lines 1, 6, 14 and 17, 30, 76 had fiber indicators characteristic of type IV.

The lowest indicator according to this sign is in the 8th series, and the metric number of its fiber is 5560. Accordingly, the relative breaking length of the fibers of these ridges is 26.8; 27.3; 28.3 and 27.0; 29.2; The fact that it is equal to 28.5 g.k/tex showed that they have an advantage over other ranges in terms of this indicator. It is known that the ridges showing the smallest fiber microneural indicators will have an advantage. Positive results in this regard were observed in rows 14 (4), 8 and 17 (4,1). For future study, the 1st ridge, the 8th ridge, the 6th ridge, especially the 14th ridge, the 17th ridge, the 30th ridge, and the 76th ridge, which have embodied signs in terms of useful signs for the economy, were singled out because of their special importance.

The best indicators among the lines in terms of fiber microneural indicators are 17th line (4.1), 14th line (4.0), 8th line (4.1), 30th line (4.1), 76-(4, 0), were found to be ridges and their fiber was found to be of high quality.

As it was mentioned above, cotton varieties that meet the requirements for all their characteristics are grown mainly for fiber, so the fiber of newly created varieties should be of good quality. For this, the goal is achieved only if the initial material used in the selection (parental forms) is long and soft. Special importance should be given to the maternal form participating in breeding.

Taking this into account, the technological indicators of the cotton crop fiber created in 2016 were analyzed by ridges.

Based on the above information, we emphasize once again that during the years 2015-2017, when the research was carried out, production of rows with positive signs, i.e. productive, type IV fiber, high technological indicators of fiber and seed moisture, resistant to cotton pests showed that it has high quality in experiments. We have given recommendations in this regard in the relevant sections.

Based on the results obtained from the scientific-research works carried out in 2015-2017 and the production experiments carried out in 2018-2019, the 17th row has a patent recommendation under the name SP-204 of the UZ NAP 00426.

Based on the results obtained from the scientific-research works carried out in 2015-2017 and the production experiments carried out in 2018-2019, the 76th row has a patent recommendation under the name SP-206 of the UZ NAP 00426 as a variety.

Among the rows, the 30th row with a positive indicator was submitted to the State Variety Testing Center under the name of Andijan-Ziyo-2.

References:

1. Abdullaev A.A. Importance of cotton gene pool. // Bulletin of agricultural science of Uzbekistan. - Tashkent, 2003. - No. 2(12).- P. 52-57
2. Abdullaev A.- "Cotton biology, selection and seed production". manual, Tashkent, 1989. 57-61 p.
3. Abdullaev A.A. Historical aspects of the evolution of early maturity of cotton.// Evolutionary and breeding aspects of early maturity and adaptability of cotton and other crops: Mat. int. scientific conf. - Tashkent: Fan, 2005. - P. 5-8.
4. Avtonomov V.A. Breeding of wilt-resistant cotton varieties with high quality and fiber yield// Cotton journal. Tashkent, 1992. - 95 p.

